

WAYS TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS OF EXPORTING ENTERPRISES IN FOREIGN MARKETS

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Abstract. In the article, in the conditions of ensuring stable growth of the economy, the production of export-oriented products in enterprises and the effective organization of their export, as well as the rational management of external and internal environmental factors, which have a significant impact on the rational use of export activities, and are the main means of its regulation, are a problem. and solutions, their causes and solutions and measures are discussed. In the article, the external and internal environmental factors that affect the export activity and increase of the potential of enterprises are studied theoretically and practically. Within the framework of the study, the most important factors of the external environment affecting the increase of the export activity and potential of enterprises and the problems arising because of its influence were analyzed. Based on the results of the research and analysis carried out by the authors, measures to solve the problems affecting export activity and potential increase were proposed and conclusions were given.

Key words: export, export activity, export potential, exporting, enterprise, external and internal environment.

INTRODUCTION

The export potential and activity of the enterprise is a component of production and financial activity, and it is characterized by full independence in choosing foreign partners, product range, contract price, size and delivery terms. This opportunity becomes more effective through proper management of the factors affecting the efficiency of export operations.

In this regard, it is increasingly important to learn how to manage the factors affecting the export potential and development of enterprises.

It should be taken into account that the external environment of the enterprise operating in the international arena is significantly different from the external environment of the enterprise operating in the national market. In addition, taking into account foreign economic activity as one of the priorities, it is very important to take into account the influence of the external environment of the potential foreign market, which is planning the activity of an export-oriented enterprise. Although in the conditions of globalization, it cannot be denied that the influence of the international environment is experienced in the domestic market, as a rule, by organizations operating in the field of competition with world producers of similar goods.

MAIN PART

Based on the analysis of the factors, we classified the factors determining the export potential of the enterprise. According to him, we divided these factors into two large groups: external and internal environment. Based on the export opportunities, we divided the

external environmental factors into direct and indirect external environmental factors. We grouped internal environmental factors into factors affecting export and factors determining export opportunities. According to him, these factors help the enterprise to effectively implement its export activities.

The study made it possible to determine the main factors affecting the export potential of enterprises.

The external environment of enterprises operating internationally is significantly different from the external environment of enterprises operating within the domestic market. In addition, the most important influence of international external environmental factors is for enterprises that are export-oriented or consider export activity as one of the priority directions. In the conditions of current globalization and liberalization of national economies, there is no doubt that the influence of the international environment is experienced by enterprises operating only within the domestic market. These are, for example, international competition, international technical and environmental standards, etc.

In addition to the factors of the external environment that affect the possibility of the external economic activity of the enterprise, there is also the internal environment of the enterprise. By the internal environment, it is the enterprise's strategy, image, management, assets, resources, research and production potential, products, the age of the main capital, financial receipts, personnel potential, market opportunities, and production opportunities of the enterprise (main production funds, their size, composition, structure, age, depreciation, labor productivity, capital productivity, etc.) are included.

So, these are the main internal environmental factors affecting the development of export activities of industrial enterprises. Taking into account these factors by developing a system of indicators describing these factors is a necessary condition for the effective development of the export activity and potential of enterprises.

One of the factors of the external environment, which significantly affects the rational use of export activity and is the main means of its regulation, is the customs system and its development tasks. The current state of the customs system, tariff regulation also characterizes the degree of liberalization of foreign trade.

In the "Doing Business 2020" study, Uzbekistan is in 152nd place among 190 countries of the world according to such an indicator as "Cross-border trade". - place and Tajikistan occupies 141st place, leaving us behind.

As a result of the reforms related to facilitating cross-border trade and simplifying customs clearance in our neighbors, Tajikistan spends 27 hours on border and customs procedures and documents (66 hours), while Kyrgyzstan spends 5 hours and 72 hours and Moldova spends 3 hours and 48 hours. If border and customs procedures in Uzbekistan require 32 hours, in Tajikistan this procedure lasts 27 hours, in Kazakhstan 105 hours, in Georgia 6 hours and in Armenia 27 hours.

In Uzbekistan, it takes 96 hours to prepare documents for international trade, 66 hours in Tajikistan, 72 hours in Kyrgyzstan, and 128 hours in Kazakhstan. In Armenia and Moldova, this procedure takes much less time: 2 and 48 hours, respectively.

Despite the progress being made, Uzbekistan is significantly lower than the countries mentioned above in terms of border and customs procedures (\$278) and paperwork (\$292).

If the export price for passing border and customs control in Uzbekistan is 278 dollars, in Tajikistan it is 313 dollars, in Kyrgyzstan it is only 10 dollars, in Kazakhstan it is 470 dollars, in Armenia and Moldova it is 100 and 76 dollars, respectively.

The price of documents for international trade in Uzbekistan is \$292, in Tajikistan \$330, in Kyrgyzstan only \$110, in Kazakhstan \$200, in Armenia and Moldova \$100 and \$44, respectively.

A study of the private sector in Uzbekistan shows that duplication of documents has become one of the main obstacles for export operations.

Thus, the number of copies of documents required for submission often reaches 200 or more pages.

Another factor that needs to be taken into account when analyzing the export activity and potential of the enterprise is the country's transport and logistics system. Increasing the potential of the enterprise's export activity and its timely and high-quality performance cannot be achieved without the formation of a cheap, high-quality and fast transport-logistics system of the state.

The logistics system, which is its lifeblood, is very important in the development of the economy of every country. By optimizing the movement of finished products and raw materials in the domestic market, an effective logistics system ensures the delivery of goods and services in favorable conditions and at low prices for customers, and stimulates competition in the market. In the foreign market, it increases the country's economic competitiveness and accelerates the process of integration into the world economy. It is very important to organize an effective logistics system for our developing country.

In the logistics efficiency report published by the World Bank in 2023, Uzbekistan ranked 88th among 160 countries. In the development of the report, criteria such as customs efficiency, quality of transport infrastructure, ease of organization of international transport, knowledge and potential of industry experts, ability to track cargo and level of timely delivery of cargo were taken into account.

CONCLUSION

In short, the effective development of the customs system and the transport-logistics system, which is considered an external environmental factor for the development of the enterprise's export activity and potential, will ensure the saving of the entire production and material resources, the acceleration of production, the reduction of transport costs and the development of economic sectors.

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